

FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION WITH LOGISTICS SERVICES IN THE CENTRAL HIGHLANDS: PERSPECTIVES FROM AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

This study examines the factors influencing the satisfaction level of agricultural producers when using logistics services in the Central Highlands. The survey data were analyzed using SEM/PLS. The results indicate that four factors positively affect satisfaction: Reliability (REL), Responsiveness (RES), Assurance (ASS) and Empathy (EMP), among which Responsiveness is the most influential factor ($\beta = 0.411$). Conversely, Tangibles are not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). The regression was determined as $SAT = 0.182REL + 0.411RES + 0.176ASS + 0.087EMP$. These findings reinforce the SERVQUAL theory in the context of agricultural logistics, while also providing practical implications for logistics enterprises to prioritize enhancing responsiveness and reliability, thereby improving customer satisfaction with logistics services in the Central Highlands.

Keywords: Influencing Factors, Satisfaction, Logistics Services, Central Highlands, Agricultural Production Enterprises.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of international economic integration, logistics plays a key role in maintaining supply chains, promoting trade, and enhancing the competitiveness of the economy. An efficient logistics system not only helps improve the quality and added value of agricultural products but also contributes to the optimal allocation of resources, cost reduction, production stimulation, market expansion and sustainable development of production areas (Nguyen., T.T.T, 2017).

Conversely, local economic and social development also serves as a solid foundation that motivates investment and expansion of logistics infrastructure, thereby creating a mutually reinforcing growth cycle. In Vietnam, logistics services are considered essential soft infrastructure for agricultural exports. The Central Highlands, a key economic region located in the South-Central part of Vietnam with its highland terrain and temperate climate, is ideal for crops such as coffee, pepper, rubber, cashew, tea, and vegetables (IDH, 2020). Therefore, the demand for logistics services in this region is becoming increasingly urgent to support the production, processing, and consumption of agricultural products.

However, the logistics system in the Central Highlands still faces many limitations. Transportation infrastructure remains underdeveloped, transportation costs are high, congestion at border gates is frequent, and storage shortages cause significant losses to agricultural products (Ministry of Industry and Trade, 2024). At the same time, the logistics workforce has not been systematically trained, and technology applications in supply chain management are still limited, reducing the competitiveness of local enterprises. The lack of connection between production and consumption, constraints in preservation and post-harvest processing facilities, and limited adoption of modern logistics technology are major reasons why logistics costs for Vietnamese agricultural products remain high, accounting for 12–38% of product costs, significantly higher than the regional average (Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, 2024).

In this context, customer satisfaction with logistics services has become a vital factor for logistics enterprises in the Central Highlands. Previous research has mainly focused on large economic centers such as Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, or seaport areas, while in-depth studies in the Central Highlands remain limited, particularly from the perspective of agricultural producers. This is a research gap that deserves attention, as the satisfaction of agricultural enterprises not only reflects the quality of logistics services but also directly affects the efficiency of exports and the added value of agricultural products in the region.

Based on this reality, the present study aims to identify the factors influencing the satisfaction level of agricultural production enterprises regarding logistics services in the Central Highlands. By applying theoretical models of service quality, it evaluates the impact of the five SERVQUAL components on customer satisfaction. From there, the paper proposes managerial implications to enhance logistics service quality, reduce supply chain costs, and increase the competitiveness of agricultural enterprises in the region.

2. THEORETICAL BASIS

2.1 Concept and Role of Logistics Services

Logistics is understood as the process of planning, implementing and controlling the flow of goods, services and information from the point of origin to the final point of consumption in order to satisfy customer needs in a cost-effective manner (Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals – CSCMP, 2013). According to the Commercial Law of Vietnam (2005), logistics services include one or more activities such as receiving goods, transportation, warehousing, customs clearance, packaging, labeling, and other services related to goods as agreed with customers.

In the agricultural sector, logistics plays a pivotal role in connecting actors within the supply chain – from producers, traders, processors, exporters, to international consumer markets. An efficient logistics system helps reduce transportation costs, minimize post-harvest losses, improve preservation quality, shorten delivery times, and enhance the competitiveness of Vietnamese agricultural products in international markets. The supply chain can be broadly summarized into the following components (An, T.T.N, 2019).

- (1) *Agricultural producers.* In Vietnam's agricultural export supply chain, inputs such as seeds, crops, and fertilizers are usually purchased from local suppliers. Farmers cultivate crops, or fishermen engage in aquaculture and fishing activities.
- (2) *Processors/Pre-processors.* These intermediaries typically purchase agricultural products from farmers. Some agricultural products may be directly procured by exporters for distribution to end consumers, such as fresh fruits or seafood. Others must undergo processing before entering distribution channels, such as rice or food products.
- (3) *Exporters.* These are enterprises responsible for exporting agricultural products abroad. In the consumption stage, Vietnamese exporters often have to use the brands of intermediaries in the importing countries. In other words, most Vietnamese agricultural products participate in supply chains without their own brands, resulting in selling mainly tangible products at only around 25% of the retail value.
- (4) *Wholesaler/Retailer.* These are large distributors with extensive networks of wholesalers and retailers in foreign markets. They handle the final distribution stage, including labeling and marketing, and capture the largest profit margins in the supply chain.
- (5) *Manufacturers.* Importers may also be manufacturers who import Vietnamese raw agricultural products for further processing. Large and well-known global manufacturers often emphasize product quality.
- (6) *Final consumer.* As the ultimate recipients, consumers are the target of the entire supply chain. They may be domestic customers (for the domestic market) or international customers (for export markets).

For agricultural products, logistics is not only a supporting tool but also a determining factor for the sustainable development of the agricultural sector. A synchronized logistics system enables agricultural enterprises to be more proactive in exports, reduce dependence on traders, and increase added value.

Conversely, limitations in infrastructure, warehousing, and logistics services will increase costs, reduce profits, and directly affect farmers' livelihoods as well as the competitiveness of local enterprises. Thus, logistics services are not merely supportive activities but rather play a crucial role in the agricultural supply chain in the Central Highlands. Improving logistics service quality will directly influence the satisfaction of agricultural production enterprises, thereby promoting regional economic development and international integration.

2.2 SERVQUAL Model

Service quality and customer satisfaction are two concepts that have been extensively studied across different service contexts. Internationally, one of the classic models commonly used to measure service quality is SERVQUAL, developed by Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry (1988). This model evaluates service quality through the difference between customer expectations and perceptions.

According to SERVQUAL, there are five main components that affect service quality:

- *Reliability*: The ability to provide promised services accurately and consistently from the first time.
- *Responsiveness*: The willingness and promptness of the enterprise in assisting customers
- *Assurance*: Knowledge, skills, courtesy, and the ability of service staff to instill trust and confidence.
- *Empathy*: The degree of care and personalized attention the enterprise gives to its customers.
- *Tangibles*: Facilities, equipment, appearance of personnel, and supporting materials.

This model has been tested and applied in many service industries, including logistics, proving its applicability and high generalization. In logistics, the SERVQUAL model has been widely employed to assess service quality and reflect customer satisfaction. Studies in both Vietnam and abroad indicate that SERVQUAL factors have positive impacts on customer satisfaction and loyalty (Cronin & Taylor, 1992; Anchal Gupta et al., 2023).

In particular, in local contexts such as the Central Highlands, where logistics infrastructure is still limited, applying the SERVQUAL model helps identify the areas that need improvement, such as delivery speed, reliability of transportation, quality of customer support, and technology adoption in order management. This has important practical implications for enhancing the satisfaction of agricultural enterprises when using logistics services in the region. Measuring customer satisfaction serves multiple purposes: providing a basis for improving service quality and increasing customer loyalty; helping enterprises capture customer experiences and adjust marketing and service strategies. It is also a key indicator of competitiveness and a predictor of long-term development.

2.3 Research Overview

Customer satisfaction in the logistics field has attracted significant attention from researchers both globally and in Vietnam. Most studies rely on foundational theoretical frameworks such as SERVQUAL (Parasuraman et al., 1988), SERVPERF (Cronin & Taylor, 1992), and other variations related to logistics service quality. These scales focus primarily on five core factors: Reliability, Responsiveness, Service Capability, Empathy, and Tangibles. However, depending on the research context, additional factors have been integrated to capture the diversity of logistics operations.

(1) International Studies

International research emphasizes the multidimensional role of logistics service quality. Mentzer et al. (2001) and Rafele (2004) highlighted order fulfillment and processing time

as key factors in assessing satisfaction. Their findings show that speed and accuracy in operations strongly affect customer satisfaction.

The study by Juga, J., et al. (2010) further emphasized operational and technical quality, arguing that, beyond customer service, safe, accurate, and efficient operations also determine long-term satisfaction. More recent studies, such as Anchal Gupta et al. (2023) in India and Xiaofang Lin et al. (2023) in China, confirmed that satisfaction plays a mediating role between service quality and reuse intention. These works underline the growing importance of information quality and personal interactions in the digital era.

(2) Domestic Research

In Vietnam, many studies have pointed out the positive impacts of these factors. For example, Vu, T.H. & Nguyen, T.B. (2021) surveyed 250 corporate customers in Northern Vietnam to analyze factors affecting satisfaction with logistics services. Based on the SERVPERF model, the study found that responsiveness, service capability, and tangibles had the strongest correlations with satisfaction. The main contribution was to emphasize the need to improve service capability and infrastructure in the context of fierce competition with international logistics corporations. However, a limitation was the lack of analysis of differences across customer groups by scale and industry.

Pham, A. K (2022) examined customer satisfaction at Cai Mep International Terminal (CMIT), a major logistics hub in Southern Vietnam. Using an extended SERVQUAL model combined with EFA and regression, the study identified six factors: resources, service capability, service processes, management capability, brand image, and social responsibility. The notable point was the inclusion of brand and social responsibility, which had previously been less emphasized. However, the study was limited to a narrow scope, focusing only on one seaport enterprise.

Bui, Q.A. et al (2025) investigated customer satisfaction with logistics service quality in Dak Lak Province – a key agricultural hub of the Central Highlands. However, this study did not consider pricing or after-sales policies, which are crucial in agricultural logistics.

The study by Nguyen, D.N & Le, T.H. (2021) on express delivery businesses in Hanoi reinforced the view that satisfaction is influenced simultaneously by service quality (responsiveness, empathy, service capability, and reliability), pricing, technology, and customer care...

(3) Research Gaps

Overall, customer satisfaction in logistics is influenced by multiple factors. SERVQUAL dimensions remain the foundation, but additional variables vary by context. Some studies added brand image and social responsibility (e.g., CMIT), others emphasized pricing and personalization (Thai Nguyen), or infrastructure and technology (Dak Lak). Several studies extended the scope to loyalty and reuse intention. Moreover, investments in human resources, infrastructure, and technology have been highlighted as essential for cost optimization and competitiveness. In Vietnam, seaport-focused studies emphasized resources and social responsibility, while agricultural provinces like Dak Lak underscored

infrastructure, transport costs, and technology. However, in the Central Highlands – where logistics are closely tied to agricultural exports – in-depth studies remain limited. This research gap underscores the need to examine the factors influencing customer satisfaction with logistics from the perspective of agricultural enterprises, providing practical evidence and managerial implications tailored to the Central Highlands.

2.4 Proposed Research Model

Based on the literature review, this study proposes the following research model:

Figure 1: Proposed research model

Source: Author's proposal

Research Hypothesis:

- H1: Reliability has a positive effect on satisfaction levels.*
- H2: Responsiveness has a positive effect on satisfaction levels.*
- H3: Assurance has a positive effect on satisfaction levels.*
- H4: Empathy has a positive effect on satisfaction levels.*
- H5: Tangibles have a positive effect on satisfaction levels.*

Table 1: Proposed Recommended Scale

Variable	Code	Scale
Reliability	REL1	Logistics companies in the Central Highlands fulfill their commitments to my company.
	REL2	Logistics companies in the Central Highlands deliver goods on time as agreed.
	REL3	Logistics companies in the Central Highlands deliver goods in full as agreed
	REL4	Customer complaints or inquiries are handled effectively and promptly.
Responsiveness	RES1	Logistics companies in the Central Highlands provide accurate information about the order status.
	RES2	Logistics companies in the Central Highlands inform customers in advance when there are changes related to the order.
	RES3	Logistics companies in the Central Highlands are always ready to assist customers when needed.
Assurance	ASS1	Logistics companies ensure the safety of customers' goods.
	AS2	Logistics companies ensure the confidentiality of customers' information.
	AS3	Logistics staff have the knowledge and skills to solve customers' problems.
Empathy	EMP1	Logistics companies prioritize meeting customer needs.
	EMP2	Logistics companies flexibly adjust service times according to customer requirements.
	EMP3	Logistics staff show care and provide dedicated support to customers.
	EMP4	Logistics companies provide personalized services according to customer requests.
Tangibles	TAN1	The logistics company's warehouses are well-equipped.
	TAN2	Logistics companies use modern technology to support services.
	TAN3	Logistics companies' vehicles meet transportation needs effectively.
Satisfaction	SAT1	My company is satisfied with the overall logistics service quality of logistics companies in the Central Highlands.
	SAT2	My company will continue using logistics services provided by logistics companies in the Central Highlands.
	SAT3	My company will recommend logistics services of logistics companies in the Central Highlands to others.

Source: Author's proposal

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data Collection Methods

Based on the theoretical foundation and the literature review of factors affecting the satisfaction of agricultural production enterprises with logistics services in the Central Highlands, the factors included in the research model consist of the following variables: (i) Reliability, (ii) Responsiveness, (iii) Assurance, (iv) Empathy, and (v) Tangibles, which

affect (vi) “satisfaction level of agricultural production enterprises in the Central Highlands”.

The quantitative research was conducted to collect opinions from agricultural production enterprises. After designing the questionnaire, the research team conducted a pilot survey with 3 randomly selected enterprises. The preliminary survey results showed that the respondents agreed with the factors included in the model. The content of the questionnaire is based on Table 1, using a 5-point Likert scale:

1. Strongly Disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neutral
4. Agree
5. Strongly agree

Due to limitations in time and resources for the survey, the author used the convenience sampling method. The minimum required sample size was calculated using the formula $n = 50 + 8m$ (m : number of independent variables) (Tabachnick and Fidell, 1996).

In the case of this study with 6 variables, the minimum number of survey forms needed was $50 + 8 \times 6 = 98$. From the perspective that collecting more observations ensures the stability of the effects, survey forms were distributed to respondents online via the Google Form link: <https://forms.gle/Ho8St6Vekts3jBcp6>. A total of 225 valid responses were collected and used for analysis.

3.2 Data Analysis Methods

The quantitative research was conducted to process the research data collected from the survey. The structural regression equation has the following general form:

$$\text{SAT} = a \cdot \text{REL} + b \cdot \text{RES} + c \cdot \text{ASS} + d \cdot \text{EMP} + e \cdot \text{TAN}$$

Methodological Approach Using SMARTPLS: SMARTPLS software was employed to test the proposed hypotheses and to assess the magnitude of the relationships among constructs. The analytical procedure followed a two-step approach:

Step 1: Measurement Model Evaluation

The assessment of the measurement model focused on reliability, indicator quality, convergent validity, and discriminant validity.

Indicator Reliability (Outer Loadings).

Outer loadings represent the degree of association between observed indicators and their corresponding latent constructs. Conceptually, these coefficients approximate the square root of the absolute value of the coefficient of determination (R^2) from the latent variable to its respective indicators. According to Hair et al. (2016), loadings should exceed 0.708, although in practice a threshold of 0.70 is widely adopted.

Internal Consistency Reliability.

Reliability was examined using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR). While Cronbach's Alpha is a conventional measure, CR is generally preferred as it provides a more accurate estimation of construct reliability (Chin, 1998). For exploratory research, CR values above 0.60 are acceptable, whereas confirmatory research requires $CR \geq 0.70$ (Henseler & Sarstedt, 2013). This criterion is consistent with earlier recommendations (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988; Hair et al., 2010). In this study, reliability was confirmed where Cronbach's Alpha ≥ 0.70 (DeVellis, 2012) and $CR \geq 0.70$.

Convergent Validity.

Convergent validity was assessed using the Average Variance Extracted (AVE). An AVE ≥ 0.50 indicates that a construct explains at least 50% of the variance of its indicators, thereby confirming adequate convergence (Hock & Ringle, 2010).

Multicollinearity.

To examine multicollinearity, variance inflation factor (VIF) values were inspected. VIF values ≥ 5 indicate problematic multicollinearity, whereas values < 5 suggest its absence (Hair et al., 2016).

Step 2: Structural Model Evaluation

Once the measurement model satisfied the above criteria, the structural model was assessed. This step examined path coefficients, the significance of hypothesized relationships, and explanatory power.

Path Coefficients and Significance Testing.

Path coefficients were evaluated using bootstrapping procedures. Key statistics included: (1) the standardized path coefficient (original sample estimate), (2) the sample mean across bootstrap resamples, (3) the standard deviation, (4) the t-statistic, and (5) the p-value. Statistical significance was determined against conventional thresholds ($p < 0.05$, 0.01, or 0.10).

Coefficient of Determination (R^2).

The explanatory power of the model was assessed using the R^2 value obtained from the PLS Algorithm results. R^2 values indicate the proportion of variance in the endogenous construct explained by its predictors, with values approaching 1 reflecting stronger explanatory capacity (Hair, Hult, et al., 2017).

In addition, when evaluating the factors, the collected data were aggregated, calculated, and presented through charts, tables, and figures using Excel software. For the factors designed according to the 5-point Likert scale, when assessing the level of influence of the factors, the average value obtained for each scale was calculated; then, the range in which the mean score lies was determined to evaluate the influence level of each factor.

$$\text{The interval value} = (\text{Maximum} - \text{Minimum}) / n = (5-1)/5 = 0.8$$

The evaluation thresholds based on the mean value are as follows:

- + 1.00 - 1.80: Strongly disagree
- + 1.81 - 2.60: Disagree
- + 2.61 - 3.40: Neutral
- + 3.41 - 4.20: Agree
- + 4.21 - 5.00: Strongly agree

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics of the Survey Sample

In this study, the authors collected 225 valid survey questionnaires from enterprises and cooperatives operating in the field of agricultural production and business in the Central Highlands. The descriptive statistics of the survey sample are presented according to two main criteria:

(1) *Types of agricultural products produced and traded by enterprises/cooperatives*

Figure 2: Classification of enterprises/cooperatives participating in the survey by type of agricultural products

Source: Survey Results

Of the total 225 enterprises/cooperatives participating in the survey, there are 88 enterprises/cooperatives (39.1%) producing coffee, accounting for the highest proportion (the Central Highlands is the largest coffee producing region in the country); 52 enterprises/cooperatives (23%) produce pepper; 27 enterprises/cooperatives (12%)

produce rubber; 38 enterprises/cooperatives (17%) produce fruits (with specialties such as durian, avocado, mango) and 20 enterprises/cooperatives (8.9%) belong to other groups (including corn, cashews, vegetables).

(2) Output market of enterprises/cooperatives

Among the enterprises/cooperatives participating in the survey, the main output market of agricultural products is domestic, with 140 enterprises/cooperatives (62.2%), showing that most units still focus on domestic consumption, especially through wholesale and retail channels within the region and neighboring provinces. Exports account for 85 enterprises/cooperatives (37.8%), mainly concentrated in coffee, pepper, and rubber. These are the key export products of the Central Highlands.

4.2 Testing of Models and Hypotheses

4.2.1 Testing the Quality of Observed Variables

The quality of the observed variables is evaluated through the outer loadings. The quality of observed variables that have an impact is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Outer loadings of factors affecting the satisfaction level of customers when using logistics services in the Central Highlands

	ASS	EMP	REL	RES	SAT	DISSOLVE
ASS1	0,857					
ASS2	0,884					
ASS3	0,807					
EMP1		0,821				
EMP2		0,708				
EMP3		0,842				
EMP4		0,837				
REL2			0,774			
REL3			0,836			
REL4			0,777			
RES1				0,821		
RES2				0,823		
RES3				0,803		
SAT1					0,932	
SAT2					0,925	
TAN1						0,820
TAN2						0,763
TAN3						0,836
REL1			0,759			

Source: Results of the research team's inspection

The results from Table 3 show that the outer loadings of all item-total correlation coefficients of the variables affecting customer satisfaction when using logistics services in the Central Highlands (all > 0.7) (Hair et al., 2016) indicate that the observed variables are significant.

Reliability Testing of Scales

The reliability of the measurement scale of factors affecting customer satisfaction when using logistics services in the Central Highlands was assessed in PLS-SEM through two main indicators:

Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR).

Table 3: Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability of factors affecting customer satisfaction when using Logistics services in the Central Highlands

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
ASS	0,807	0,810	0,886	0,722
EMP	0,816	0,822	0,879	0,646
REL	0,795	0,800	0,867	0,620
RES	0,748	0,749	0,856	0,665
SAT	0,841	0,842	0,926	0,862
DISSOLVE	0,737	0,757	0,848	0,651

Source: Results of the research team's inspection

According to Table 3, after analyzing and testing the reliability using Cronbach's Alpha of the factors, the results are: (i) Reliability reached 0.795; (ii) Responsiveness reached 0.748; (iii) Assurance reached 0.807; (iv) Empathy reached 0.816; (v) Tangibles reached 0.737; affecting (vi) Satisfaction of agricultural production enterprises in the Central Highlands (SAT) which reached 0.814.

Thus, all the scales satisfy the condition > 0.7 (DeVellis, 2012) and do not violate any rules requiring variable elimination; therefore, no variable was removed and the reliability is acceptable.

The Composite Reliability (CR) of all observed variables is also > 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988) (Table 3). Therefore, the scale is reliable, has analytical significance, and is used in subsequent factor analysis.

Convergence

According to the results of data analysis in Table 4, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values of the factors are: (i) Reliability 0.620, (ii) Responsiveness 0.665, (iii) Assurance 0.722, (iv) Empathy 0.646, (v) Tangibles 0.651, and (vi) Satisfaction of agricultural production enterprises in the Central Highlands 0.862.

Thus, the AVE values of all variables are greater than 0.5 (Hock & Ringle, 2010), showing that the model satisfies the conditions of convergence.

Discriminant Validity

The results in Table 4 of the Fornell-Larcker criterion of the research model of factors affecting customer satisfaction when using logistics services in the Central Highlands (BI): (i) Reliability, (ii) Responsiveness, (iii) Assurance, (iv) Empathy, and (v) Tangibles all

ensure discriminant validity because all the square root values of AVE on the diagonal are higher than their off-diagonal values.

Therefore, in terms of discriminant validity, both criteria, cross-loadings and the Fornell–Larcker criterion, satisfy the required conditions (Fornell, D.F. Larcker., 1981).

Table 4: The Fornell-Larcker indicator of the research model is a factor affecting customer satisfaction when using logistics services in the Central Highlands

	ASS	EMP	REL	RES	SAT	DISSOLVE
ASS	0,850					
EMP	0,398	0,804				
REL	0,416	0,416	0,787			
RES	0,520	0,462	0,546	0,815		
SAT	0,504	0,430	0,519	0,647	0,929	
DISSOLVE	0,355	0,550	0,268	0,414	0,342	0,807

Source: Results of the research team's inspection

f² Value

The f^2 value represents the extent of influence of a construct (factor) when it is removed from the model. The f^2 values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 correspond to small, medium, and large effects (Cohen, 1988) of the exogenous variable, respectively. If the effect size is < 0.02 , it is considered to have no effect.

Table 5: Summary table of f^2 values

	ASS	EMP	REL	RES	SAT	DISSOLVE
ASS					0,041	
EMP					0,009	
REL					0,042	
RES					0,183	
SAT						
DISSOLVE					0,000	

Source: Results of the research team's inspection

In this model, as shown in Table 5, the factors Empathy (EMP) and Tangibles (TAN) have $f^2 < 0.02$, considered as having no effect; Assurance (ASS) and Reliability (REL) have $0.02 < f^2 < 0.15$, indicating a medium effect; Responsiveness (RES) has $0.15 < f^2 < 0.35$, indicating a large effect on customer satisfaction (SAT) with logistics services in the Central Highlands.

Results of Assessing the Influence Level Using the Structural Model

Evaluation of Influencing Relationships

Regarding the relationships and the influence level of the factors affecting customer satisfaction when using logistics services in the Central Highlands on SMARTPLS, they are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Factors affecting customer satisfaction when using logistics services in the Central Highlands

Source: SMARTPLS accreditation results of the research team

The results of the Bootstrap analysis to evaluate the influencing relationships are shown in Table 6. Accordingly, the variables: (i) Reliability, (ii) Responsiveness, (iii) Assurance, and (iv) Empathy have P Values < 0.05 (*hypotheses H1, H2, H3, and H4 are accepted at the 5% significance level*). The variable (v) Tangibles has no effect on customer satisfaction (SAT) when using logistics services in the Central Highlands, as this factor has P Values > 0.05 (*hypothesis H5 is not accepted at the 5% significance level*).

Table 6: Path Coefficient

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean(m)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
ASS -> SAT	0,176	0,175	0,060	2,951	0,003
EMP -> SAT	0,087	0,088	0,050	1,740	0,083
REL -> SAT	0,182	0,185	0,052	3,482	0,001
RES -> SAT	0,411	0,407	0,063	6,532	0,000
TAN -> SAT	0,013	0,020	0,057	0,222	0,824

Source: SMARTPLS accreditation results of the research team

The testing results in Table 6 show that with 95% confidence level,

- (i) Reliability,
- (ii) Responsiveness,
- (iii) Assurance, and
- (iv) Empathy have an effect on customer satisfaction (SAT) when using logistics services in the Central Highlands.

Thus, the regression equation is as follows:

$$\text{SAT} = 0.182 \cdot \text{REL} + 0.411 \cdot \text{RES} + 0.176 \cdot \text{ASS} + 0.087 \cdot \text{EMP}$$

The coefficients are all positive, consistent with hypotheses H1, H2, H3, and H4, indicating a positive effect on customer satisfaction (SAT) when using logistics services in the Central Highlands

Evaluate the Overall Coefficient that Determines R² (R Square)

The result of the PLS analysis gives an R², which reflects the explanatory power of the independent variables for the dependent variable.

The R² index measures the coefficient of determination (R-square value), which is an indicator to measure the model's goodness of fit (the explanatory power of the model). According to Hair & et al. (2010), the proposed R-square values are at the levels of 0.75, 0.50, or 0.25.

Table 7: Explanatory power of independent variables for the dependent variable (R Square)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
SAT	0,491	0,479

Source: Results of the research team's inspection

The results from Table 7 show that R² of the "satisfaction factor" - SAT equal to 0.491 and R² corrected for 0.479 - was appropriate in this study case.

Thus, the independent factors explain 49.1% of the factor "customer satisfaction when using logistics services in the Central Highlands (SAT)".

5. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND SOME PROPOSALS

5.1 Discussion of Results

"Customer satisfaction when using Logistics services in the Central Highlands (SAT)" is the central dependent variable of the model, reflecting the satisfaction level of customers when using logistics services in the Central Highlands. The survey results of the three SAT scales reflect the overall satisfaction (SAT1), the intention to continue using (SAT2), and the intention to recommend (SAT3) of agricultural production enterprises in the Central Highlands regarding logistics services, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Mean values of the variable "Satisfaction/Behavioral Intent (SAT)"

Code	Express	Mean Score	Level of Agreement
SAT1	" My company is satisfied with the overall logistics service quality of logistics companies in the Central Highlands."	3,529	Agree
SAT2	" My company will continue using the logistics services of logistics companies in the Central Highlands."	3,520	Agree
SAT3	" My company will recommend the services of logistics companies in the Central Highlands to others."	2,893	Neutral

Source: Survey Results

Among three scales, SAT1 “My company is satisfied with the overall logistics service quality of logistics companies in the Central Highlands” achieved the highest mean score (3.529), showing that agricultural production enterprises tend to have a positive assessment of the current service quality. SAT2 “My company will continue using the logistics services of logistics companies in the Central Highlands” achieved a similar mean score (3.520), reflecting a relatively clear intention of customers to maintain cooperation, although not really outstanding. Meanwhile, SAT3 “My company will recommend the services of logistics companies in the Central Highlands to others” has a lower mean score (2.893), remaining at a neutral level.

These results indicate that although enterprises are satisfied and willing to continue using the services, they do not yet have enough confidence to recommend the services to other partners. In other words, logistics companies in the Central Highlands have relatively met the basic requirements but have not reached the “exceeding expectations” level for customers to be willing to spread positively.

This is an important indicator of the gap between basic satisfaction and advocacy-level loyalty (WOM) (Oliver, 1993). Considering the characteristics of mountainous terrain, distance from seaports, and the seasonality of agricultural products in the Central Highlands, logistics service providers in this region need to enhance the preservation of agricultural product quality, compensation services for losses, and cost transparency; thereby increasing satisfaction and customers’ behavioral intentions to use the service? This question is answered through further research into the impact of each factor on customer satisfaction.

The SEM/PLS analysis results with 95% confidence show that among the five factors included in the model, the factors (i) Reliability, (ii) Responsiveness, (iii) Assurance, and (iv) Empathy affect “Customer satisfaction (SAT) when using logistics services in the Central Highlands.” The factor (v) Tangibles has no effect on “Customer satisfaction (SAT) when using logistics services in the Central Highlands” because this factor has a P value > 0.05. Thus, the regression equation is as follows:

$$\text{SAT} = 0.182 \cdot \text{REL} + 0.411 \cdot \text{RES} + 0.176 \cdot \text{ASS} + 0.087 \cdot \text{EMP}$$

(1) Effect of Reliability (REL) on Satisfaction (SAT)

With a regression coefficient of 0.182, REL has a positive effect on SAT, implying that agricultural production enterprises in the Central Highlands only maintain and value logistics services when companies fulfill their commitments, deliver in full and on time, and handle problems effectively. This result is consistent with previous studies on logistics service quality based on the SERVQUAL model, in which Reliability is often the fundamental factor strongly influencing customer satisfaction (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Nguyen, D.N., & Le, T.H., 2021).

Table 9: Reliability Scale Results – REL

Code	Scale	Mean Score	Level of Agreement
REL1	Logistics companies in the Central Highlands fulfill their commitments with my company.	3,582	Agree
REL2	Logistics companies in the Central Highlands deliver goods on time as agreed.	3,511	Agree
REL3	Logistics companies in the Central Highlands deliver goods in full as agreed.	3,498	Agree
REL4	Customer complaints or inquiries are resolved effectively and promptly.	3,493	Agree

Source: Survey Results

The mean scores of all four items of REL reached the “agree” level, reflecting that agricultural production enterprises have a fairly positive evaluation of the reliability of logistics services in the Central Highlands.

Among them, customers particularly value the fulfillment of commitments regarding time, cost, and agricultural product preservation processes (REL1 achieved the highest mean score of 3.582).

In contrast, REL4 (3.493) had the lowest score, reflecting limitations in complaint handling and customer support, which are important in the context of perishable and high-risk agricultural products.

A previous study in Thai Nguyen by Nguyen Thi Kim Tuyen (2025) also indicated that reliability (especially timeliness and completeness) positively affects logistics satisfaction. This reinforces the findings in the Central Highlands, emphasizing the importance of on-time delivery and adherence to contractual commitments.

(2) Effects of Responsiveness (RES)

With a regression coefficient of 0.411, RES is the factor with the strongest effect on SAT, implying that agricultural production enterprises in the Central Highlands especially value quick responses, timely information provision, and customer support when problems arise. This result is consistent with previous studies in logistics, where Responsiveness is considered an important measure of service quality, directly affecting customer experience and retention decisions (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Nguyen Thi Kim Tuyen, 2025).

Table 10: Responsiveness Factor Survey Results

Code	Scale	Mean Score	Level of Agreement
RES1	Logistics companies in the Central Highlands provide accurate information about order status.	3,453	Agree
RES2	Logistics companies in the Central Highlands notify customers in advance when there are changes related to orders.	3,413	Agree
RES3	Logistics companies are always ready to support customers when needed.	3,360	Neutral

Source: Survey Results

Agricultural enterprises in the Central Highlands generally have a positive evaluation of responsiveness and support. Among them, RES1 (3.453) achieved the highest score, showing that information on order status is provided relatively accurately. When problems or delivery delays occur, logistics service providers update and inform customers (RES2 scored 3.413).

However, RES3 (3.360) had the lowest score, only reaching the neutral level, reflecting that the readiness to support customers when needed is not yet outstanding, especially in the context of perishable agricultural products requiring quick responses when incidents occur during transportation.

In the specific context of the Central Highlands, delivery depends heavily on road infrastructure, weather, and crop seasonality. Therefore, quick responsiveness and transparent information help agricultural enterprises be more proactive in production and consumption planning. According to Zeithaml & Bitner (1996), when customers feel that the service provider is “by their side” in uncertain situations, satisfaction and loyalty increase significantly.

(3) Effect of Assurance (ASS)

With a regression coefficient of 0.176, ASS has a positive impact on satisfaction (SAT), showing that the assurance factor is an important foundation for agricultural enterprises to trust and maintain cooperation with logistics companies in the Central Highlands. This result is consistent with the SERVQUAL theory (Parasuraman et al., 1988), in which Assurance reflects customers’ sense of security and trust when using the service.

Table 11: Assurance Survey Results

Code	Scale	Mean Score	Level of Agreement
ASS1	Logistics companies ensure the safety of customers’ goods.	3,978	Agree (close to the strongly agree)
ASS2	Logistics companies ensure the confidentiality of customers’ information.	3,916	Agree
ASS3	Logistics staff have the knowledge and skills to solve customers’ problems.	3,547	Agree

Source: Survey Results

The three “assurance” scales, including ensuring goods safety, information confidentiality, and staff competence, all reached “agree,” reflecting positive customer evaluation. Among them, ASS1 (3.978) achieved the highest score, showing that goods safety is the top priority for agricultural enterprises, especially with perishable products such as coffee, durian, and fresh fruits. ASS2 (3.916) reflects customers’ trust in information confidentiality commitments. However, ASS3 (3.547) is lower, indicating that logistics staff’s professional competence and problem-solving skills still need improvement, especially given the unexpected risks in agricultural transport (cold chain failures, traffic congestion, seasonal delays). This result is consistent with research in the Mekong Delta (Tran Thi Bach Yen & Tran Thi Kim Dung, 2020), where Assurance was proven to be an important factor in building trust for SMEs in logistics services. Thus, Assurance plays a role in increasing customers’ perceived safety and trust, thereby enhancing overall satisfaction.

(4) The Effect of Empathy (EMP)

With a regression coefficient of 0.087, EMP has a positive but weaker effect compared to other factors in the model on SAT. Empathy, expressed through care, listening, and service personalization, plays a supplementary role in enhancing perceived value in customer experience.

Table 12: Empathy Survey Results

Code	Scale	Mean Score	Level of Agreement
EMP1	Logistics companies prioritize meeting customer needs.	3,702	Agree
EMP2	Logistics companies flexibly adjust service times according to customer needs.	3,058	Neutral
EMP3	Logistics staff show care and provide dedicated support to customers.	3,649	Agree
EMP4	Logistics companies provide personalized services according to customer requests.	3,658	Agree

Source: Survey Results

The results of the Empathy factor show that enterprises recognize logistics companies’ efforts in prioritizing customer needs (EMP1 scored 3.702); acknowledgment of staff care (EMP3 scored 3.649) and personalized services (EMP4 scored 3.658). These results reflect that staff attention and personalized services are emphasized. However, EMP2 (3.058) remains at a neutral level, showing limitations in flexibility in adjusting service times, which is particularly important in the agricultural sector with seasonality and the need for quick transport after harvest.

This result is consistent with international studies (Mentzer et al., 2001; Bienstock et al., 2008), which suggest that Empathy has a positive but usually weaker effect compared to Reliability or Responsiveness in logistics. In Vietnam, research by Hoang et al. (2020) also confirmed that although empathy is less prioritized, it remains a factor that creates competitive differentiation in long-term relationships.

5.2 Some Suggestions

The research results show that customer satisfaction with logistics services in the Central Highlands is mainly influenced by the factors Responsiveness (RES), Reliability (REL), Assurance (ASS), and Empathy (EMP).

Among these, RES has the strongest impact, followed by REL and ASS, while EMP has a weaker effect. To enhance satisfaction and encourage customers not only to continue using the service but also to be willing to recommend it, several specific managerial proposals are suggested as follows:

(1) Responsiveness (RES)

In the context of complex terrain, limited transport infrastructure and high seasonality of agricultural products, providing fast, transparent and flexible services is a prerequisite for agricultural enterprises to appreciate service quality. Logistics businesses need to:

- Build an early warning system: Logistics companies need to invest in an IT system that allows timely notification of incidents (traffic jams, schedule changes, bad weather), helping agricultural enterprises proactively adjust production and distribution.
- 24/7 customer support center: Establish online support teams and dedicated hotlines to respond immediately when customers encounter problems, especially during the harvest season of coffee, durian, and pepper. These are products that require short transit times and specialized transportation vehicles.
- Digital platform application: Popularize online tracking, chatbot support, and customer portal to provide real-time transparent information.

(2) Reliability (REL)

Customers are satisfied when logistics providers fulfill commitments, deliver in full, and handle problems effectively. Therefore, to strengthen reliability, logistics companies need to:

- Standardize service commitments: Make clear commitments about delivery times, completeness, and compensation policies in case of violations. The standardization of service commitments should be flexibly adjusted according to the specific seasonality of each type of agricultural product in the Central Highlands
- Apply transport monitoring technology: Equip devices to monitor temperature and humidity for fresh produce, while providing electronic documentation to ensure transparency in the delivery process.
- Improve the efficiency of complaint handling: Shorten the time to receive and handle complaints for customers

(3) Assurance (ASS)

Corresponding to the 3 **Assurance scales (ASS)** including cargo safety, information security and employee capacity, proposals to improve assurance include:

- Ensuring cargo safety: Investing in a system of cold storage, refrigerated containers with standards and clear cargo insurance so that customers can be assured of the quality of agricultural products after transportation.
- Information security: Develop data management systems in accordance with international standards, applying blockchain in bill of lading management to minimize forgery risks.
- Employee professional training: Organize periodic training on operational techniques, risk management, and customer communication skills to help staff handle incidents flexibly and professionally.

(4) About Empathy (EMP)

Although empathy has a smaller impact on customer satisfaction according to the survey results, it remains important in creating personalized service experiences and fostering long-term attachment. Logistics companies need to:

- Increase service flexibility: Adjust delivery schedules according to customers' actual needs during peak seasons; design specialized service packages for each type of agricultural product.
- Proactive customer care: Staff should regularly survey customer needs, visit key customers, and provide dedicated support in unexpected situations.
- Personalized services: Develop personalized "customized logistics" service packages tailored to customer needs, such as special transport routes for large shipments, or provide individual dashboards for each customer to track orders in detail.

(5) Some other suggestions

- Investment in logistics infrastructure in raw material areas: Establish inter-regional logistics centers in key production areas for each type of agricultural product, taking into account seasonal characteristics and preservation requirements, to reduce collection costs from farms to warehouses.
- Government's support policies: Propose tax incentives, interest rate support for investment in refrigerated vehicles, and encourage digital transformation in logistics in the Central Highlands.
- Value chain cooperation: Promote linkage models between logistics enterprises, agricultural cooperatives, and export companies to ensure stable outputs and enhance competitiveness across the entire chain.

6. CONCLUSION

This study focuses on analyzing the factors affecting the satisfaction of agricultural production enterprises when using logistics services in the Central Highlands. The survey results and SEM/PLS analysis indicate that among the five factors included in the model (Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, and Tangibles), only four factors—REL, RES, ASS, and EMP—have significant effects on satisfaction, while Tangibles are statistically insignificant. Thus, the study contributes to clarifying the determinants of customer satisfaction with logistics services among agricultural enterprises in the Central Highlands. The results not only have academic significance by reinforcing the SERVQUAL theory in the specific context of Central Highlands logistics but also provide practical value for logistics enterprises and policymakers in improving service quality and better meeting the needs of this strategic agricultural region in Vietnam. Nevertheless, the measurement scale was mainly based on the SERVQUAL model, which, although widely validated, has not integrated emerging factors such as digital transformation, environmental sustainability, or government policy, which can significantly affect logistics today. Future research may add new variables such as the application of digital technologies (AI, IoT, Blockchain), sustainability (green logistics), and relative logistics costs to reflect the development trends of modern logistics services.

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